

A Service Provider's Guide to Data Sharing Policies

These reference cards convey data sharing policy recommendations to be adopted by data and service providers within the EOSC-hub consortium.

Our recommendations contribute to the developing field of data sharing policies in the EOSC at large.

The Why | **The What** | The How

What are essential concepts in the context of data sharing policies in the EOSC-hub ecosystem?

For more details, consult the D2.8 and D2.9 deliverables via:
<https://bit.ly/2zDAAnM>

A model for FAIR digital objects

All shareable data objects in the EOSC-hub ecosystem should be FAIR Digital Objects.

FAIR Data Objects are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. A FAIR ecosystem ensures a number of data services and components to be in place that enable FAIR data⁵.

Offered through EOSC-hub is a variety of services that implement these concepts such as EGI DataHub⁶ and the EUDAT B2 Service Suite⁷.

The components of a FAIR ecosystem

Data objects in the EOSC-hub ecosystem should adopt licences from the Creative Commons 4.0 licence suite.

Where data are openly shareable, these should be one of: CC BY 4.0 (attribution), CC BY SA 4.0 (attribution with onward propagation), CC0 (public domain or rights waiver)⁸.

The EOSC-hub B2SHARE service, for example, hosts a tool to help the user choose the correct licence for their data⁹.

LICENSING

NOTES

5] S.Hodson, S.Jones et al, Turning FAIR into reality, European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data, November 2018, <https://bit.ly/2YvDJPX>

6] <https://bit.ly/2CHKURB>

7] <https://bit.ly/2CzM24Q>

8] <https://bit.ly/2VbCund>

9] <https://bit.ly/2YxPIDv>